

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3 Section 3.3.1.2: Fragmentation of ecosystems

Version: 1

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8035352

Project leader and contributors:

- Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)

- Jan Pergl (jan.pergl@ibot.cas.cz)

Data curator(s):

- Jan Pergl (jan.pergl@ibot.cas.cz)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.3.1.2 assesses the role of spatial fragmentation of ecosystems as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Search 1 were conducted for the first order draft, then based on the external reviewer's comment, additional Search 2 to 6 were conducted.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: TOPIC: (habitat* and fragmentation* and (invas* or alien* or weed*)) AND YEAR 6118 PUBLISHED: (2000-2019)

Search 2: (invasi*) AND (fragment*) AND (Species OR population* OR habitat* OR ecosystem* OR biodiversity OR conservation OR metapopulation* OR "genetic diversity")

Search 3: Search 2 + contain the word 'review'

Search 4: Search 3 + contain the phrase "systematic review"

Search 5: TITLE (invasi*) AND (fragment*) AND (Species OR population* OR habitat* OR ecosystem* OR biodiversity OR conservation OR metapopulation* OR "genetic diversity")

Search 6: TITLE (invasi*) AND TITLE (fragment*) AND (Species OR population* OR habitat* OR ecosystem* OR biodiversity OR conservation OR metapopulation* OR "genetic diversity")

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Searched time period:** 2000-2019

- **Date:**

Search 1: June 2020

Search 2-6: November 22, 2021

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

Search 1: 21
Search 2-6: 0

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type (review) excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2-6:

Downloaded the abstracts for the 10 papers selected from Search 4 and the 119 hits with strict title search from Search 6. Looked through the 10 papers of Search 4 first, none were useful. Then looked Search 6 result and went through the normal papers newest-first (this was mainly because Search 2 to 6 were conducted to correspond to the external reviewer's comment that the section didn't appear up-to date). None of the papers match to the scope of the study. Main reasons for not including papers were that the invasive species was the driver (independent) variable), the search term "fragment*" picking up studies of spread by root/stem fragments, the search term "invas*" picking up non-invasive genetic sampling methods, or studies carried out in fragmented landscapes without the effect of fragmentation itself being tested or controlled for.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 0

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed:21 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx